

EBFMC25-OP-07 · Adaptation of the Gosnell Pressure Ulcer Risk Assessment Scale to Turkish: Validity and Reliability Study

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ABSTRACT

Objective: This study aimed to adapt the Gosnell Pressure Ulcer Risk Assessment Scale into Turkish and to evaluate its linguistic validity, content validity, inter-observer reliability, and construct validity through exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses (Celdran-Manas et al., 1999; Gosnell, 1989)

Materials and Methods: This methodological study was conducted with 150 patients treated in a palliative care unit over one year. The adaptation process consisted of two stages: linguistic validation and assessment of validity and reliability. Linguistic validity was assessed using the translation-back translation method and expert reviews (Hancer, 2003). Content validity was evaluated using the Lawshe technique with input from five experts from the Department of Family Medicine (Alpar, 2022). Reliability was assessed by measuring inter-observer agreement using the Kappa coefficient, Cramer's V coefficient, and Spearman correlation analysis.

To evaluate construct validity, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) using Principal Component Analysis and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) using the Diagonally Weighted Least Squares (DWLS) estimation method were conducted (Yesilyurt & Capraz, 2018).

Results: A total of 150 participants were included, with a mean age of 74.74 years, and 58% were female. The Content Validity Ratio (CVR) for each item was calculated as 1. Regarding reliability, the Kappa coefficient for the Mental Status item was 0.903, and Cramer's V coefficient was 0.896; for the Continence, Mobility, and Activity items, both the Kappa and Cramer's V coefficients were 1. For the Nutrition item, the Kappa coefficient was 0.840, and Cramer's V coefficient was 0.862. A significant and positive correlation was found between the total scores of the two observers ($p < 0.001$). For construct validity, the EFA revealed a single-factor structure explaining 62.039% of the total variance, with a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value of 0.783 and Bartlett's test of sphericity being significant ($\chi^2(10) = 383.266, p < 0.001$). The subsequent CFA showed a marginal model fit ($\chi^2/df = 5.627$), while all factor loadings were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The Nutrition item demonstrated a relatively lower loading (0.457), suggesting possible cultural or contextual differences in the Turkish sample.

Conclusion: The Turkish version of the Gosnell Pressure Ulcer Risk Assessment Scale was found to be a valid and reliable tool for use by healthcare professionals in Turkey. The scale showed acceptable content and construct validity. However, the Nutrition item should be further examined in future studies to improve its cultural appropriateness and statistical consistency.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Pressure ulcer, risk assessment scale, validity, reliability

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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